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Enhancing Tank Farm Pipeline Protection using Electrical Monitoring Technique

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ABSTRACT

Steel pipelines for hydrocarbon conveyance usually suffer from galvanic or electrolytic corrosion impact. Their life-span is affected because they deteriorate with time. The consequences of corrosion impacts with associated failures affect the environment, economy, public health and safety. This study seeks to examine the improvement of tank farm pipeline protection using electrical method. The electrical method for the protection of the tank farm pipeline using impressed current cathodic protection system is one out of the many strategies available in protecting the pipeline and other metallic structures buried in soil against corrosion effects in the soil. Corrosion of tank farm pipelines in Nigeria presents a critical challenge, leading to frequent failures, environmental hazards, and substantial economic losses. Existing corrosion protection methods, such as sacrificial anode systems have proven inadequate under the harsh environmental conditions in Nigeria. This study explores the use of impressed current cathodic protection (ICCP) to improve the protection of the pipelines. The source of current is photovoltaic ICCP, which offers a more effective solution by providing consistent and controllable corrosion resistance thus, increasing the length of time of the pipelines thereby lowering the cost of maintenance. This was achieved by burying into the soil two metallic pipes of about 300cm by 2.54cm with a thickness of 0.01cm at Akwete, Abia State, Nigeria. One pipe was protected while the other was not. The photovoltaic cell negative terminal was tied to the protected pipe while the anode was extended and buried at depths of 25cm, 35cm, 45cm, 55cm, 65cm, 75cm, 85cm, 95cm, and 105cm, respectively. From the results obtained, depths of 25cm and 35cm satisfied the protection requirement but the cathodic protection was

very high as observed from the depth of 65cm with a degree of protection of 96.54%.

Keywords:- *Impressed Current Cathodic Protection, sacrificial anode systems, Tank farm, Pipeline protection, pipe-to-soil potential*

INTRODUCTION

Impressed Current Cathodic Protection (ICCP) is an electrical method used for the control of corrosion of metals. This method prevents metals from rusting especially when imposing an opposing electrical voltage between the metal and the ground. The method helps to protect all steel structures have contact with all types of environment. The protection covers the interiors and outer surfaces of the metallic structures in any environment.

The integrity of tank farm pipelines is essential to provide efficient transportation and storage of products which are critical to Nigeria's oil and gas sector [1]. However, these pipelines are frequently subjected to bad environment and corrosive soil chemistries, accelerating the process of corrosion. Impressed current cathodic protection (ICCP) is a sophisticated method that involves applying a continuous and controllable electrical current to the pipeline to mitigate corrosion.

Unlike sacrificial anodes, ICCP systems can be fine-tuned to maintain optimal protection levels, making them particularly suited for complex and extensive pipeline networks typical of tank farms. This method not only provides a more consistent level of protection but also has the ability to adapt to the varying environmental and operational conditions found in Nigeria [1].

RELATED WORKS

The successful adoption of ICCP for tank farm pipelines promises to enhance the

longevity and reliability of these critical infrastructures, reduce maintenance and repair costs, and significantly lower the risk of environmental contamination and safety hazards. Ultimately, this advancement aligns with Nigeria's broader goals of achieving sustainable and resilient oil and gas operations, safeguarding both the environment and the economy [2].

Corrosion detection and prevention using crystalline hydrotalcite particulate additives was investigated [3]. Investigation of localized corrosion of metals due to coating error using localized technique is encouraged [4]. Organic products serve to a large extent in the prevention of corrosion of metals or steel structures even in corrosion prone environment [5].

The method that can be employed to assess the level of corrosion that may also provide a controlled process in corrosion activities was recommended [6]. Coupons are used for the monitoring of the adequacy of the cathodic system of protection of pipeline and were observed to be adequate for monitoring of the system [7].

Data on potential and current for numerical analysis to evaluate the extent of corrosion protection of a cathodically protected pipeline are available [8]. Efficient and economic corrosion prevention can be achieved through an anode in the inner surface of water pipes. Tape ribbon sacrificial anodes are ideal for the cathodic protection of buried pipelines.

Solar PV-powered mini-cathodic system of protection was found to be ideal for cathodic protection utilizations.

The objectives of this work are to analyze:

- i. The chemical properties of the soil samples.
- ii. The solar irradiance of the site.
- iii. The potential tests of pipe making contact with soil when impressed current is used and when impressed current is not used.
- iv. The penetrometer soil profile (PSP) data at different depths.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The following instruments were used to determine the effect of variation of depths on applied photovoltaic current for the cathodic corrosion protection of metal pipelines: two Siemens Sm 66 model rated 55 Watts with a short circuit current of 3.45A and voltage of 17.4V, photovoltaic modules, one Steca Omega Model 30A charge controller with a voltage rating of 12/24V and current rating of 12A, one 100AH Delco deep cycle solar battery, an ALDA AVD 838 digital multimeter, a griffin foreign galvanometer with ranges from 0 to 10A.

All of the above materials were sourced from the Energy Research Centre stores. The measuring tape, ungalvanized pipes, 100m electrical connecting cables, measuring cylinder, nuts and bolts were purchased from the Akwete Ogige Market. The Cu/CuSO₄ reference electrode was blown to shape.

Methods

The photovoltaic cell assembly was designed. Cables of about 50cm in length were connected to the pipes at equal distances with the help of bolts and nuts. The pipes were labelled A for the protection, and B for the control. Two trenches about 25cm depth and parallel to

each other were dug in the field between the administrative buildings of the fossil oil tank farm in Akwete in Abia state.

The trenches were labelled X for the protected pipe and Y for the control also. The distance between X and Y was about 1500cm. Site X was for the protected while Site Y was for unprotected which was for control. Thereafter, pipe A was tied to the negative terminal of the solar photovoltaic (SPV) system. Pipe B was not connected to any electricity.

The solar electric power positive part was tied to anode at Site X about four meters away from the protected pipe. The anode was made of a metal bar 20cm long, 7.5cm wide and 4mm thick. The anode had a four-meter connecting cable attached to it with the help of the bolt and nut. The depths of the anode were varied beginning from 20cm to 100cm at 10cm intervals. At a depth of 10cm, the anode was above ground. Below 100cm depth, it was difficult to get in and out of the manhole.

The pipes were observed for about 30 days for each depth by taking records of both the pipe and its contact with the soil potential and the current three days a week and three times a day on the days of monitoring. The measurements were taken at 3- hourly intervals starting at 9.00 am local time on each day. There was no anode at Site Y. The measurement of the potential between the pipe and the soil was affected by electrical multimeter.

The current measurement was made possible using galvanometer. Both the current and potential between the pipe and soil obtained were averaged and shown in the tables used in the analysis. The experimental period started from the dry season into the rainy season and then repeated during the dry season of the second year.

Fabrication of Saturated Cu/CuSO₄ Reference Electrode

The saturated reference electrode, being Cu/CuSO₄ was constructed at the laboratory. The instrument was made of a 20cm glass tube, a 30cm copper rod, two wooden corks, copper sulphate crystals and deionized water. The 20cm glass tube was blown such that both ends were enlarged to hold wooden corks as shown in Figure 1. A saturated copper sulphate solution was prepared in the glass tube by

dissolving excess copper sulphate crystals in distilled water. Excess copper sulphate crystals were always maintained in the solution. The potential for the constructed saturated copper sulphate reference electrode was +0.32V with respect to the standard hydrogen electrode. Electrical contact was made only through the porous wooden plug, which was kept moist by seepage of CuSO₄ solution.

Fig.1:-Saturated Electrode

Soil Sample Analysis

Before burying the pipes, samples were collected from the trenches. The samples were labelled SX and SY respectively. SX represented the protected site while SY was the unprotected site as mentioned earlier. The pH and electrical conductivity of the samples were measured. The soil samples from both sites were collected and analyzed both at the beginning and the end of the experiment. The analyses were performed at the Soil Science Laboratory, University of Agriculture Benue State.

Potential Testing between Pipe and Soil with Impressed Current

The potential tests between pipe and soil with impressed current were carried out on site X which was connected to the SPV generating system as shown in Figure 2. The charge controller positive output was connected to anode A while the negative output was connected to pipe A making the pipe a cathode. The cables were securely held on the pipes with the aid of metal screws and bolts. The electrode was placed at positions 0.0, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0,

2.5, and 3.0m along each of the pipes at soil level and the pipe to soil readings was recorded.

Fig.2:-Potential Test between Pipe and Soil using Impressed Current

Potential Assessment of Pipe and Soil Contact with Changes in Depth

The pipe and soil contact potential measurement was carried out on both Sites X and Y with the help of the reference electrode (Cu/CuSO₄) as stated in the experiment. The measurement of pressure sensor performance (PSP) was taken three days a week. The monitoring at each depth was carried out for a month at each depth. The anode depths used for the experiment included 25cm, 35cm, 45cm, 55cm, 65cm, 75cm, 85cm, 95cm, and 105cm, respectively. The potential measurement between the pipe and the soil was conducted at different anode depths and the current was monitored for a month at each depth.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Result of Soil Specimen Analysis

The level of corrosion is dependent a number of factors. However, cathodic

corrosion protection depends more on the pH and electrical conductivity. The soil contents for the location of the study were then monitored for pH and electrical conductivity both before and after the experiment.

The results of the analysis both before and after the experiment are shown in Table 1. It was observed that site X had a pH value of 6.4 while site Y was 4.9. Thus, site Y is more acidic than site X.

The soil samples were analyzed after the earlier measurements and the results were as shown in Table 1 in which the pH values for sites X and Y were 6.3 and 4.8 respectively. This showed that both sites X and Y remained close to their pH before the experiment with only a slight increase in acidity. The E.R. is shown in Table 1 for both sites before and after the experiment.

Table 1: Chemical Properties of Soil Samples before and after the Experiment

Sample	Before			After		
	pH	Conductivity (µs per cm)	Resistivity (Ω per cm)	pH	Conductivity (µs per cm)	Resistivity (Ω per cm)
Site SX	6.4	6.8	14,706	6.3	6.6	15,152
Site SY	4.9	9.0	11,111	4.8	9.2	10,870

Result of Solar Irradiance

The result of the averaged data of solar irradiance on the hour on the days of the experiment. Solar radiation is already high as early as 8 am having averaged about 201W/m² for the duration of the project as contained in Table 2. The solar radiation continued to rise until it peaked at about noon. The insolation dropped but was still

strong at 16h. At the 16h, it was about 358W/m². The solar radiation produced the current that maintained the battery at the green indicator of charge. The solar radiation therefore generated the current needed for the protection of the pipe for the duration of the project at all times including at night and during periods of low insolation.

Table 2:-Average Solar Irradiance vs Time for the Days of Project

Time in Hrs	8	9	12	15	16
Insolation (W/m ²)	200.96	412.54	671.57	491.82	357.81

The plot of the solar radiation against the time of day is shown in Figure 3.

Fig.3:-Graph of the Average Solar Insolation Data Against Time on Days of Study

Results of Potential Testing between Pipe and Soil with Impressed Current

The potential measurement between pipe and soil was obtained in the presence and absence of applied current and the control without current was measured for the pipes by taking the PSP measurements from seven different points along the pipelines. The results in Table 3, the pipe-to-soil potentials without current, (i.e. the control), show some slight differences in the static potential values. This indicates that there was no homogeneity in both the metal surface and the soil resistance along the pipeline. Such differences reveal the presence of galvanic microcells and the tendency of galvanic corrosion to occur along the pipe at different points.

Also, the potential between the pipe and soil obtained with the current on pipe A was below the protection zone, i.e. below - .850V along the entire surface of the pipe. This shows that the potential between the pipe and soil generated was appropriate to protect the pipes. Therefore, the current produced by the photovoltaic system was enough to protect the pipes. Moreover, the potential between the pipe and soil produced along the pipe was not below - 2000mV and therefore not excessive to generate hydrogen gas.

Also, the current that produced the potential between the pipe and soil at each location was measured and is shown in Table 3 that the current varied at different

positions along the pipe such that at length 0.0, the current was 7.8amps, at 0.5m the current was 8.4amp and at 3.0m the

current was 6.2amp, etc. This showed that the current along the pipe surface was not constant.

Table 3:- Potential between Pipe and Soil in the Presence and Absence of impressed current and control

Length of pipe (m)	Without impressed current (mV)	With impressed current (mV)	Control (mV)
	Pipe A	Pipe A	Pipe B
0.0	-208	-1549	-229
0.5	-311	-1155	-205
1.0	-357	-987	-207
1.5	-253	-1189	-220
2.0	-257	-1064	-213
2.5	-252	-1016	-214
3.0	-254	-1453	-246

Results of the PSP Data at Different Depths

The current and potential between the pipe and soil data generated at different depths were averaged. Site X was protected while site Y was unprotected and therefore the control. The averaged pipe-to-soil potential for both the protected and the control were plotted against the length of the pipe based on Ohm’s Law. In Tables 4 to 5, \bar{p} represents the average pipe-to-soil potential data in mV while \bar{i} represents the average current producing the potential between the pipe and soil at that position in amperes. Also, the mean data were analyzed statistically using SPSS 16.

The effectiveness of protection is expressed by the inhibition coefficient γ or the degree of protection, Z. The degree of

protection shows to what extent the corrosion is depressed by the method used and is calculated from the following equation:

$$Z = \frac{V^1 - V^2}{V^1} \times 100 \tag{1}$$

where V^1 is the mean potential after protection and V^2 the mean potential before protection.

Table 4 represents the average PSP and current data at 25cm depth for both sites X and Y. Site X is the site under protection while site Y is the control. The Table contains the averaged current and potential data for both the protected and unprotected sites. The mean current value is represented by \bar{i} in amperes while the mean potential value between pipe and soil is represented by \bar{p} (mV).

Table 4:-Average Data for Anode Depth at 25cm

Length(m)	Site X			Site Y		
	\bar{p} (mV)	\bar{i} (A)	$\log \bar{i}$	Length(m)	\bar{p} (mV)	\bar{i} (A)
0.0	-1171.11	6.47	0.811	0.0	-260.78	0
0.5	-934.11	6.04	0.781	0.5	-296.17	0
1.0	-891.56	6.39	0.806	1.0	-289.56	0
1.5	-864.11	6.35	0.802	1.5	-270.72	0
2.0	-849.55	6.37	0.804	2.0	-258.28	0
2.5	-930.28	6.52	0.814	2.5	-265.83	0
3.0	-1283.56	6.26	0.796	3.0	-252.89	0
Mean 1.500	-989.2	6.3429	0.802	1.500	-270.60	0
St Dev 1.080	168.8	0.1577	0.01097	1.080	16.32	0

Figure 4 is the graph of average PSP data against pipe length at 25cm depth. In the diagram, the PSPc represents the potential of control (without current) while the PSP is the potential with current (under protection). The PSPc is the pipe-to-soil potential generated by the metal B in the soil. The PSPc in Figure 4 is almost a horizontal line starting from about -252mV, rising to -300mV and then dropping to the -252mV level indicating microcell activities along the surface of the pipe while the PSP for metal A under protection is a curve. The protection curve PSP started from about -1173mV and rose

to about -940mV and continued to rise to almost -850mV before dropping again to about -1290mV. However, the PSP was not excessive as it reduces the possibility of hydrogen evolution. The protection criterion was met [9]. The degree of protection was calculated using Equation 1 and was found to be 71.63%.

The statistical analysis at 25cm depth under protection i.e sit X showed a mean PSP of $\pm 989.18\text{mV}$ and a standard deviation of $\pm 168.8\text{mV}$. The mean PSP and the standard deviation for sit Y (the control) were $\pm 270.60\text{mV}$ and $\pm 16.32\text{mV}$. Respectively.

Fig.4:-Graph of Pipe to Soil Potential vs Length at 25cm Dept

Table 5 contains both the average current and PSP data obtained at 35cm depth.

Table 5:-Average Data for Anode Depth at 35cm

Site X				Site Y		
Length(m)	\bar{p} (mV)	\bar{i} (A)	$\log \bar{i}$	Length(m)	\bar{p} (mV)	\bar{i} (A)
0.0	-1307.61	6.40	0.806	0.0	-326.33	0
0.5	-989.28	6.28	0.798	0.5	-377.39	0
1.0	-915.67	6.41	0.807	1.0	-366.17	0
1.5	-856.22	6.35	0.802	1.5	-323.06	0
2.0	-854.22	6.28	0.798	2.0	-306.33	0
2.5	-981.33	6.41	0.807	2.5	-322.61	0
3.0	-1382.17	6.40	0.805	3.0	-306.83	0
Mean 1.500	-1040.9	6.3614	0.80329	1.500	-332.7	0
St Dev 1.080	215.4	0.0593	0.00399	1.080	28.0	0

Figure 5 shows the plot of average pipe-to-soil potential data vs pipe length at 35cm depth. PSPc starting from about -326.33mV showed more pronounced fluctuations than that at 25cm depth. The almost horizontal line had disappeared with a more pronounced rise to about -380mV, then dropping to about -325mV and continuing to about -300mV before rising again to about -320mV and then dropping to about -305mV indicating increased corrosion activity. The PSP is a curve that started from about -1310mV

dropping to almost -850mV before rising to about -1380mV. There an almost 400mV depression from PSPc to PSP. The protection criterion was met. The protection pipe to soil potential was not excessive and therefore hydrogen evolution is not predicted. The degree of protection was 68.04% [10].

The mean PSP and the standard deviation for sit X were ± 1040.9 mV and 215.4mV respectively, while the average mean PSP and the standard deviation for sit Y were ± 332.7 mV and ± 28.0 mV, respectively.

Fig.5:-Graph of Pipe to Soil Potential vs Length at 35cm Depth

From the preceding results, it was observed that only three depths namely 25, 35, and 65cm met the protection criterion. The degree of protection was 96.54% at 60cm, 68.04% at 35cm and 71.63% at 20cm respectively. The efficiency was 33.3%.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, it was observed that using impressed current cathodic protection (ICCP) improved tank farm pipeline protection which offers several significant advantages. The primary benefit of ICCP is that it is effective in preventing corrosion, which can extend

the lifespan of pipelines and reduce maintenance costs. By applying a continuous and controllable electrical current to the pipeline, ICCP ensures more consistent and reliable protection compared to other methods like sacrificial anode systems.

ICCP provides superior protection against corrosion by maintaining a constant current, which is particularly beneficial for large and complex pipeline networks in tank farms. Although the initial setup cost for ICCP can be higher than other methods, the long-term benefits, including reduced maintenance, fewer repairs, and

extended pipeline lifespan, result in overall cost savings. ICCP systems offer precise control and easy monitoring, allowing for real-time adjustments to ensure optimal protection levels. This ability to fine-tune the system helps in addressing specific corrosion issues promptly. ICCP is adaptable to varying environmental conditions and pipeline materials. This flexibility makes it suitable for diverse tank farm configurations and operational scenarios.

Adopting impressed current cathodic protection for tank farm pipelines significantly enhances corrosion resistance, improves operational reliability, and offers long-term economic benefits. With proper design, installation, and maintenance, ICCP stands out as a robust solution for safeguarding pipeline infrastructure in tank farms.

Finally, it was observed that the CP effectiveness can be very high as observed from the depth of 65cm with a degree of protection of 96.54%. The nature of the soil/pH affected the quantity of electricity required to protect the pipe and Akwete soil is relatively not corrosive. The position and depth of the anode affected the cathodic protection of the metal.

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